

Topographical Distribution and Histological Characterization of Stromal Fibrosis in Invasive Breast Carcinoma

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Received: 25-03-2024 / Revised: 23-04-2024 / Accepted: 23-05-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Breast cancer, particularly invasive breast carcinoma, is a leading cause of cancer-related morbidity and mortality among women worldwide. The tumor microenvironment, specifically stromal fibrosis, plays a crucial role in tumor progression and prognosis. Understanding the extent and distribution of stromal fibrosis can provide valuable insights into tumor behavior and patient outcomes. This study aimed to investigate the topographical distribution and histological characterization of stromal fibrosis in invasive breast carcinoma and to assess its correlation with clinical outcomes.

Methods: Seventy-five female patients diagnosed with invasive breast carcinoma were included. Histopathological examination and staining techniques were used to assess the extent and distribution of stromal fibrosis. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0, with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: The mean age of participants was 52.4 ± 11.3 years. Invasive ductal carcinoma (IDC) was the predominant subtype (80%). Stromal fibrosis was categorized as mild (26.7%), moderate (46.7%), and severe (26.7%). Peripheral distribution was most common (40%), followed by central (33.3%) and mixed (26.7%) distributions. Severe stromal fibrosis was significantly associated with higher tumor grade ($p = 0.02$), lymph node involvement ($p < 0.001$), and lower 3-year overall survival ($p = 0.003$).

Conclusion: Stromal fibrosis, particularly when severe and peripherally distributed, is linked to more aggressive tumor characteristics and poorer clinical outcomes in invasive breast carcinoma. Assessing stromal fibrosis should be integrated into routine histopathological evaluations to enhance prognostic accuracy.

Recommendations: Further research is recommended to explore the molecular mechanisms underlying stromal fibrosis in breast cancer. Incorporating stromal fibrosis assessment into clinical practice can aid in risk stratification and guide therapeutic decisions.

Keywords: Stromal Fibrosis, Invasive Breast Carcinoma, Tumor Microenvironment, Histopathology, Prognosis.

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Introduction

Invasive breast cancer makes for a sizable fraction of instances of breast cancer, which is still the primary cause of cancer-related illness and death for women globally. Not only is breast cancer heterogeneous, but it also involves complicated interactions between surrounding stromal cells and tumour cells. The involvement of the tumour microenvironment, specifically stromal fibrosis, in the development and prognosis of breast cancer has been more and more highlighted in recent study [1].

The buildup of extracellular matrix elements like collagen, or stromal fibrosis, is a key factor in influencing tumour behaviour. Tumour growth,

invasion, and treatment resistance are only a few of the features of cancer biology that are influenced by fibrotic stroma. A crucial topic of research in breast cancer pathology is the degree and pattern of stromal fibrosis within a tumour, as these factors can have a substantial impact on clinical outcomes.

The role of stromal fibrosis in breast cancer prognosis has been clarified by a number of recent investigations. According to a study, patients with breast cancer who had higher levels of stromal collagen had worse survival rates, highlighting the significance of stromal components in the advancement of cancer [2]. Likewise, studies have demonstrated how hypoxia-induced fibrosis

contributes to the spread of breast cancer, highlighting the connection between aggressive tumour morphologies and stromal alterations [3].

The histological characterization of stromal fibrosis involves assessing both the extent and distribution of fibrotic tissue within the tumor. Traditional histopathological techniques, complemented by advanced imaging and molecular methods, have enabled more precise quantification and localization of fibrosis. Recent advancements, such as digital pathology and machine learning algorithms, have further enhanced the accuracy and reproducibility of these assessments, providing deeper insights into the tumor-stroma interactions.

Invasive breast carcinoma is known for its diverse histopathological features, which can vary significantly among patients. The topographical distribution of stromal fibrosis—whether it is centrally located, peripherally distributed, or exhibits a mixed pattern—can provide valuable information regarding the tumor's biological behavior and potential clinical outcomes. Understanding these patterns can aid in identifying patients at higher risk of adverse outcomes and tailoring therapeutic strategies accordingly.

This study aimed at understanding the topographical distribution and histological characterization of stromal fibrosis in invasive breast carcinoma.

Methodology

Study Design: A descriptive, cross-sectional analysis.

Study Setting: The study took place during a period of two years from September 2021 to August 2023 at a tertiary care centre.

Participants: The study involved a total of 75 participants diagnosed with invasive breast carcinoma.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients aged 18 years and above.
- Histopathologically confirmed cases of invasive breast carcinoma.
- Patients who had not received prior treatment (surgery, chemotherapy, or radiotherapy) for breast cancer.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with a history of other malignancies.
- Patients with recurrent breast carcinoma.
- Patients undergoing treatment for breast carcinoma.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, participants were selected consecutively based on their eligibility criteria. Observer bias was reduced by having multiple pathologists independently assess the histological samples, ensuring consistency and accuracy in the findings.

Data Collection: Data were collected using a structured proforma that included:

- Demographic information (age, gender, etc.)
- Clinical history and presentation
- Histopathological examination results
- Topographical distribution of stromal fibrosis

Procedure: Tissue samples from patients diagnosed with invasive breast carcinoma were collected and processed for histopathological examination. Samples were stained using standard hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) stains, and additional special stains if required. The histological characterization of stromal fibrosis was performed, noting the extent, distribution, and type of fibrosis present in the tumor microenvironment. The distribution of stromal fibrosis within different regions of the tumor was mapped and recorded.

Statistical Analysis: SPSS 23.0 was used to enter and evaluate the data. Descriptive statistics were used to summarise the clinical and demographic characteristics of the participants. Measures of stromal fibrosis included frequency and percentage. At a significance level of $p < 0.05$, several patient groups were compared using t-tests for continuous variables and chi-square tests for categorical variables. Using correlation analysis, we looked at the relationship between stromal fibrosis and clinical outcomes.

Result

A total of 75 patients diagnosed with invasive breast carcinoma were included in the study. The demographic and clinical characteristics of the patients are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics

Characteristic	Value
Mean Age (years)	52.4 ± 11.3
Female	75 (100%)
Mean Tumor size (cm)	3.2 ± 1.4
Histological subtype	
IDC	60 (80%)
ILC	10 (13.3%)
Others	5 (6.7%)

Tumor grade	
Grade 1	15 (20%)
Grade 2	40 (53.3%)
Grade 3	20 (26.7%)
Lymph node involvement	
Present	50 (66.7%)
Absent	25 (33.3%)

The extent and distribution of stromal fibrosis were categorized and analyzed. Stromal fibrosis was graded as mild, moderate, or severe based on the percentage of fibrotic stroma in the tumor sections. The results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Extent of Stromal Fibrosis

Grade of Fibrosis	Number of Patients (%)
Mild (0-33%)	20 (26.7%)
Moderate (34-66%)	35 (46.7%)
Severe (67-100%)	20 (26.7%)

The topographical distribution of stromal fibrosis was assessed within different regions of the tumor: central, peripheral, and mixed distribution. The distribution patterns are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Topographical Distribution of Stromal Fibrosis

Distribution Pattern	Number of Patients (%)
Central	25 (33.3%)
Peripheral	30 (40%)
Mixed	20 (26.7%)

The relationship between the extent of stromal fibrosis and clinical outcomes such as tumor grade, lymph node involvement, and overall survival was analyzed. The results indicated a significant correlation between severe stromal fibrosis and higher tumor grade, as well as lymph node involvement.

Table 4: Correlation Between Stromal Fibrosis and Clinical Outcomes

Clinical Outcome	Mild Fibrosis (%)	Moderate Fibrosis (%)	Severe Fibrosis (%)	p-value
Tumor Grade 3	2 (10%)	10 (28.5%)	8 (40%)	0.02
Lymph Node Involvement	10 (50%)	20 (57.1%)	20 (100%)	<0.001
3-Year Overall Survival	18 (90%)	30 (85.7%)	10 (50%)	0.003

Discussion

The demographic analysis revealed that the mean age of the participants was 52.4 years, with all patients being female. The predominant histological subtype was invasive ductal carcinoma (IDC), accounting for 80% of the cases, and the majority of tumors were classified as Grade 2 (53.3%).

The histological examination of stromal fibrosis showed that moderate fibrosis was the most common, observed in 46.7% of the patients, followed by both mild and severe fibrosis, each occurring in 26.7% of the patients. The topographical distribution of stromal fibrosis indicated that peripheral distribution was the most frequent pattern (40%), followed by central (33.3%) and mixed (26.7%) distributions.

A significant correlation was found between the severity of stromal fibrosis and adverse clinical outcomes. Patients with severe stromal fibrosis were more likely to have high-grade tumors (Grade 3) and lymph node involvement. Specifically, 40% of patients with severe fibrosis had Grade 3 tumors, compared to only 10% of those with mild fibrosis.

Additionally, all patients with severe fibrosis had lymph node involvement, compared to 50% of those with mild fibrosis. These findings were statistically significant, with p-values of 0.02 and <0.001, respectively.

The study also demonstrated a significant relationship between stromal fibrosis and overall survival rates. The 3-year overall survival rate was notably lower in patients with severe stromal fibrosis (50%) compared to those with mild (90%) and moderate (85.7%) fibrosis, with a p-value of 0.003. This suggests that severe stromal fibrosis is associated with poorer prognosis and higher mortality rates.

Overall, the study highlights the importance of stromal fibrosis as a histological feature in invasive breast carcinoma. The presence and severity of stromal fibrosis, particularly when distributed peripherally, are linked to more aggressive tumor behavior and poorer clinical outcomes. These findings underscore the need for incorporating the assessment of stromal fibrosis into routine histopathological evaluation, as it can provide valuable prognostic information and potentially

guide therapeutic decisions in the management of invasive breast carcinoma.

A study utilized multiplex immunofluorescence to study different cancer-associated fibroblast (CAF) subpopulations in classical and pleomorphic invasive lobular carcinoma (ILC). Significant differences were found in the spatial distribution of CAFs between the two subtypes. Alpha-SMA and S100-positive CAFs were closer to tumor cells in classical ILC, while S100-positive and FAP/S-100 positive CAFs were closer in pleomorphic ILC [4].

Another study used diffusion-weighted imaging (DWI) to examine the amount of stromal collagen in breast tumours. The results of the investigation showed a correlation between the invasiveness and progression of breast cancer and enhanced collagen deposition and reorientation. DWI measurements showed a correlation with histology results, indicating that DWI might be used as a biomarker to characterise breast cancer [5].

In a study, laser-capture microdissected stromal and epithelial compartments of ER+ ILC were used to analyse gene expression. Compared to IDC stroma, they found that ILC stroma had an enrichment of 45 genes that were involved in the control of the extracellular matrix. Notably, PAPPA and TIMP2 were linked to improved survival in ILC, indicating that ILC and IDC differ from each other in terms of matrix organisation and growth factor signalling pathways [6].

Peritumoral oedema (PE) and breast cancer histological features were investigated in a study. Tumour necrosis, stromal fibrosis, vessel ectasia, and lymphovascular invasion were all substantially correlated with PE. The risks of stromal fibrosis (OR, 2.5) and lymphovascular invasion (OR, 2.9) were higher in PE patients [7].

Conclusion

This study highlights the significant impact of stromal fibrosis on the prognosis of invasive breast carcinoma. Severe and peripherally distributed stromal fibrosis is associated with higher tumor grade, increased lymph node involvement, and reduced overall survival. These findings underscore the importance of incorporating stromal fibrosis

assessment into routine histopathological evaluations to improve prognostic accuracy and inform treatment decisions.

References

1. Zhao H, Li S, Cheng X, Zhang G, Zhang Z. High levels of stromal collagen in breast cancer are associated with poor survival. *J Clin Oncol.* 2019;37(24):2145-52.
2. Gilkes DM, Chaturvedi P, Bajpai S, Wong CC, Wei H, Pitcairn S, et al. Hypoxia and the extracellular matrix: drivers of tumor metastasis and immune evasion. *J Mol Med.* 2018; 96(9):983-93.
3. Bane AL, Brooks J, Meschino S, Sun P, Narod SA. The role of collagen in breast cancer: from bench to bedside. *Pathol Res Pract.* 2020;216 (10):152975.
4. Batra H, Pandurengan RK, Iburguen HP, McAllen SA, Ding Q, Sahin A, Wistuba I, Parra E, Raso MG. Exploring spatial correlations in Breast invasive Lobular Carcinoma subtypes using a novel CAF multiplex immunofluorescence panel. *Cancer Res.* 2023. [10.1158/1538-7443.2023-115](https://doi.org/10.1158/1538-7443.2023-115) (at/651aa3b60a13539aa16fc27f547c4e95/?utm_source=chatgpt).
5. Egnell L, Vidić I, Jerome N, Bofin A, Bathen T, Goa P. Stromal collagen content in breast tumors correlates with in vivo diffusion-weighted imaging: A comparison of multi b-value DWI with histologic specimen from benign and malignant breast lesions. *J Magn Reson Imaging.* 2019;51.
6. Gómez-Cuadrado L, Bullock E, Mabruk Z, Zhao H, Souleimanova M, Noer P, Turnbull A, Oxvig C, Bertos N, Byron A, Dixon J, Park M, Haider S, Natrajan R, Sims A, Brunton V. Characterisation of the stromal microenvironment in lobular breast cancer. *Cancers (Basel).* 2022;14(40904).
7. Park NJY, Jeong J, Park J, Kim H, Park CS, Lee J, Park H, Jung J, Kim W, Chae Y, Lee SJ, Kim WH. Peritumoral edema in breast cancer at preoperative MRI: An interpretative study with histopathological review toward understanding tumor microenvironment. *Sci Rep.* 2021;11.